

In searching for the Past and Present of Saraswati Worshipping among the Jain Community of Bengal and Jharkhand: A Historical Discourse

Siddhartha Das*

In terms of religious variety and diversity in the cultural periphery of India, Jainism is one of those religions and sects that were able to steer the country's culture and tradition in a new direction. Historically, the era of the 24th Tirthankara Mahavira, i.e. the fifth century BCE (circa), is generally identified as the time of the emergence of Jainism or its popular-most variant¹, but many scholars acknowledged the existence of the Jainism and the Jain community from the time of Mahavira's first ancestor, the first Jain *Tirthankara R̥ṣabhadeva* or *Ādideva*². However, it is widely accepted that since the early days of Jainism, the Jain community lived in the ancient *Aṅga* and *Vaṅga mahājanapadas* of Eastern India and this community was known as *Śrāvakas*. A distorted pronunciation of the word 'Sravaka' is 'Sarāk'³, by which this early Jain sect is better known today. There is an opinion, though controversial, that the Sravaka community played a key role in the spread of new civilization and craft culture in the aforesaid regions⁴. Even the matter about early arrival of copper⁵ and iron⁶ culture in the prehistoric Bengal region has been attributed to them by many historians. The existential references of this community are also found in mediaeval Bengali literature⁷. In the modern era, several British officials and field surveyors have described the original and contemporary behavior of this *Sarāk* or *Śrāvaka* community in their accounts. Today, this historical community can be seen living in some selected areas in *Rādha* or *Lādha* region of West Bengal, Bhum region of Jharkhand and several places of Odish⁸. In this paper, an attempt has been made by the author to understand Saraswati worshipping and its ancient traditions among these communities by revisiting archaeological findings, studying some literary works and conducting fieldwork in selected parts of Jharkhand and West Bengal.

*UGC Junior Research Fellow & former Field Investigator, ICSSR Major Research Project

Saraswati, younger daughter of lord Shiva and Parvati, is a very popular goddess in Hinduism, who is generally worshipped as the goddess of wisdom, knowledge, speech (*Vāk*), music and learning. Saraswati is considered an important Goddess in Jainism also.

A group of historians and scholars claimed that in Jainism, the Goddess became known as "*Saraswati*" or "*Śrūtadevatā*" during the Kushana era, approximately circa 200 CE⁹. The wisdom and divine power of the Goddess are proclaimed by the *Jina Purusha* and *Kevalajñāni* or *Kevalins* in the sacred Jain Agama texts such as *Vyākhyā Prajnapti* and *Paumacharya*. Apart from these, references to 'Śrūtadevatā' or 'Saraswati' are found in *Pannabagaran* (Pali pronunciation of *Pancha Vyākaraṇa*), *Bhagavatī Sūtra*, *Mahāniśīthasūtra*, and many other Jain scriptures also. The Jain tradition describes the twelve Jain *Āṅgasūtras* as the limbs of the Goddess and the fourteen *Pūrvas* as her ornament¹⁰. In the Jain text '*Ratnasāgara*' it is said in praise of Goddess Saraswati-

Kundēndu-gōkṣīra-tuṣārabarnā
sarōjahastā kamalē niṣannā.
Bāgīśvarī pustakabargahastā
*sukhāya sā na: Sadā praśastā.*¹¹

In the same book, Goddess Saraswati is also referred to as '*Viśwarupiṇi*'. Jain scriptural writers refer to Goddess Saraswati by a total of sixteen names, including *Bharati*, *Sāradā*, *Bāgīśvarī*, *Brahmani*, *Brahmavādini*, *Bratacāriṇi* etc¹². Goddess Saraswati was initially worshipped as the embodiment of wisdom and purity, but from the 10th century CE she was also worshipped as the Goddess of music¹³ in Jain culture.

The Jain sculptures of the Goddess Saraswati belonging to the early period that are found across India have two hands¹⁴. In some sculptures she is seen with a rose in one hand and a lotus on the other. In others, she is seen with a water-pot (*kamaṇḍalu*) and a rosary (*jaṇḍamālā*) in her two hands¹⁵. Later sculptures, especially from the 10th-11th centuries CE, are four-armed, with ladle and book in the two upper hands and rosary and vessel in the lower two. But in both cases the swan is present at her feet, as the vehicle (*vahana*) of the Goddess¹⁶. One of the sculptures of the Goddess Saraswati was discovered inside a dilapidated *pañcāyatana* temple in Wari village under Harishchandra Pur police station of Malda¹⁷. In this sculpture, the Goddess is seated in *Lalitāsana* or *Ardhaparyankasana*. Although the Goddess is represented as multi-handed in the sculpture, all the arms of the sculpture are in a damaged state i.e. there is nothing left of the original. However, many experts have speculated that the number of hands in the sculpture could be either eight or ten. An inscription was found on the pillar of the statue itself, which was later deciphered by renowned epigraphist Dinesh

Chandra Sircar. The inscription states that this sculpture of Goddess Saraswati was installed by honorable Padmagiri, in his (Padmagiri's) place of worship (*Param ārādhyā*) (temple?) built of baked bricks, who is isolated from all external world. However, the fact is that the sculpture has ten (or eight) hands which create confusion in the minds of researchers about the real identity of the deity. Because, until this discovery, almost all the Hindu and Buddhist canonical scriptures usually identify the Goddess Saraswati with two, four or at the most six arms. In addition, the determination of the actual period of the statue or the writing is not historically conclusive. On the other hand, researcher-professor Bijan Mandal during his research fieldwork observed several different figures of Goddess Saraswati¹⁸. One of these figures, founded in Golahat village in Burdwan, is currently worshipped as "*Jaymangalā*" outside the new temple structure as per the beliefs and demands of local people. Another figure found at Ghazal in Malda district of West Bengal is similar to the previous one. In both cases, the "buffalo rider" or *mahiṣavāhini* form of the goddess is seen, which is also an exception. These exceptional figures, according to Dr. Mondal, are representation of local traditions and beliefs of Devi's worshipping¹⁹. On the other hand, it is surprisingly true that the earliest Jain Saraswati figure was discovered from the Kankali Tila in Mathura, but later, most of the Jain Saraswati sculptures were found in western and central India and some places in the southern India. Several temples of Baroda in Gujarat, Udaipur in Rajasthan, Mount Abu Pahar, Bikaner, Khajuraho in Madhya Pradesh, especially the Pārśwanātha temple, are noteworthy in this regard.

The figures found at all these places bear some resemblance to the previously discussed Saraswati figures of indeterminate style found in Bengal. Here, the style of holding the veena, the presence of rosary (*akṣamālā*) in the right hand, the water pot in the left hand, the physical adornment etc. are noteworthy. In this matter, it may not be unreasonable to assume that the Jain style of sculpture of western India has an influence on all those declassified sculptures of Bengal mentioned earlier. However, it is not yet appropriate to declare the figures to be solely Jain Saraswati idols.

Although the Jain community of Bengal is mentioned sporadically in mediaeval literature and some colonial writings, there is almost no information about their religious rituals, especially about worshipping of Devi Saraswati. Nowadays, several researchers have worked on various aspects of *Sarāk* life, such as socio-economic status, culture, rituals etc., but they have almost ignored the tradition of Saraswati worshipping among that community. The fact is, a clear and healthy deviation can be observed in the religious practices of the *Sarāk* Jain community nowadays, in which mainly the influence of Hinduism is seen to a

greater extent. Therefore, many scholars and researchers may have noticed the matter of Saraswati worshipping in the community, but they have avoided it by simplifying it as an effect of Hindu influence.

The present author conducted surveys in Belut²⁰ village in Bokaro district and Rangalia²¹ village in Dumka district of Jharkhand basically for a project funded by Indian Council for Social Science Research. The author conducted similar surveys in Gobag²² and Lachia²³ villages in Purulia district of West Bengal also. All of those villages in which the present author did surveys are predominantly inhabited by the Jain *Sarāk* community. The presence of Saraswati temples is observed in each of these villages. During the surveys, some older members of the community told the author that the tradition of worshipping Devi Saraswati in a structured building or temple has been continuing since time immemorial. Although Saraswati is one of the eminent goddesses of Hinduism, her permanent temple is not seen in the niche of Hindu culture, especially in Hindu areas of West Bengal and this is where it differs from Hindu culture. Besides, through various interviews conducted during the survey phase, it is known that such temples exist in other *Sarāk* -inhabited villages around the region. Therefore, it can be considered as a distinct form of Saraswati worshipping of the *Sarāks* living in those areas mentioned before.

[Acknowledgement: The author would like to express his sole gratitude to Dr. Anupam Jash, under whose supervision the author played a cameo as a field investigator for the esteemed ICSSR major research project work on the livelihood of the *Sarāk* community living in West Bengal and Jharkhand. The author also wants to thank Bitan Chakraborty, an independent journalist-cum-researcher by nature, who read and corrected the proof by wasting his valuable time.]

Notes & References:

1. Chatterjee Asim Kumar (2000), *A Comprehensive History of Jainism*, Vol. 1, 2nd Edition. New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers Pvt. Ltd., 33.
2. Bothra, Lata (2013), "Jainism in Bengal", in *Development & Impact of Jainism in India and Abroad*, ed. Gunvant Barvalia, Mumbai: Arham Spiritual Centre's Saurashtra Kesari Pranguru Jain Philosophical & Literary Research Centre, 121.
3. Majee Judhishthir (2001), *Sarāk Samskriti O Puruliar Purakeerti*, Kolkata: Jain Bhavan, p. 15.
4. Bothra, op.cit. 121.
5. V. Ball, (1869) "On the Ancient Copper Mines of Singbhum" in *Proceedings of The Asiatic Society of Bengal*, Calcutta: The Asiatic Society.
6. Majumder R. C. (1943), *History of Bengal*, Vol-1. Dacca: University of Dacca, pp. 409-410.
7. Majee, *Ibid*, 7.
8. Tiwari Binod Kumar (2013) "The Forgotten Religious Heritage of the 'Sarāk a' Community of Bengal, Orissa and Jharkhand", in *Development & Impact of Jainism in India and Abroad*, ed. Gunvant Barvalia, Mumbai: Arham Spiritual Centre's Saurashtra Kesari Pranguru Jain Philosophical & Literary Research Centre, p. 61.
9. Tiwari Dr. Maruti Nandan Pd. & Sinha Dr. Shanti Swaroop (2024) "Concept of Saraswati in Jain Tradition and Art", *Indian Journal of Archaeology*, 677. <http://ijarch.org/Admin/Articles/5-Sarasvati%20in%20jain%20tradition%20&%20art.pdf>, Accessed on January 13, 2024.
10. Sonawani Sanjay (2024), "Saraswati in Jainism: A Study", 3. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375004358_Saraswati_in_Jainism_A_Study, Accessed on January 16, 2024.
11. Jagadishwarananda Swami (1980), *Shree Shree Chandi*, Edited & Translated, 4th Edition, Kolkata: Udbodhan Karyalay, p.12.
12. *Ibid*, 13.
13. Tiwari & Sinha, op.cit., 678.
14. Sankalia, H. D. (2024) "Jaina Iconography", 347-348. <https://archive.org/details/ac1cp100000694a1426>, Accessed on May 10, 2024.
15. *Ibid*.
16. *Ibid*.
17. Saha, Sharmila & Sanyal, Rajat (2022), "Notes on a 'Unique Instance' of Sarasvati from North Bengal", in *Monthly Bulletin*, 51, no. 2, 32-34.
18. Mondal Bijan (2022) "Images of a Distinct Regional Tradition: Sarasvati on Ram in Bengal", in *Monthly Bulletin*, 51, no. 2, pp38-40.
19. *Ibid*, 40.

20. Here, survey was conducted on 28 and 29 November of 2023 based upon a structured research questionnaire.
21. Survey Conducted on 8 January of 2024.
22. Survey Conducted on 15 October, 2023.
23. Survey Conducted on 11 November, 2023.